

Pointwise weighted approximation of functions with inner singularities by Bernstein operators

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Abstract.

We consider the pointwise weighted approximation by Bernstein operators with inner singularities. The related weight functions are weights $\bar{w}(x) = |x - \xi|^\alpha (0 < \xi < 1, \alpha > 0)$.

In this paper we give direct and inverse results of this type of Bernstein polynomials.

Keywords: Pointwise weighted approximation; Bernstein operators; inner singularities.

1 Introduction

The set of all continuous functions, defined on the interval I , is denoted by $C(I)$. For any $f \in C([0, 1])$, the corresponding *Bernstein operators* are defined as follows:

$$B_n(f, x) := \sum_{k=0}^n f\left(\frac{k}{n}\right) p_{n,k}(x),$$

Where

$$p_{n,k}(x) := \binom{n}{k} x^k (1-x)^{n-k}, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n, \quad x \in [0, 1].$$

Approximation properties of Bernstein operators have been studied very well. Berens and Lorentz showed in [1] that

$$B_n(f, x) - f(x) = O\left(\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} \delta_n(x)\right)^{\alpha_1}\right) \iff \omega^1(f, t) = O(t^{\alpha_1}),$$

where $0 < \alpha_1 < 1$, $\delta_n(x) = \varphi(x) + \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$, $\varphi(x) = \sqrt{x(1-x)}$.

It is well known that approximation of functions with singularities by polynomial is of special value in both theories and applications. As an important type of polynomial approximation, approximation of functions by Bernstein operators is an important topic in both approximation theory and computational theory, which plays an important role in neural networks, fitting data, curves, and surfaces. Some work has been done by [2]. Throughout the paper, C denotes a positive constant independent of n and x , which may be different in different cases.

Let $\bar{w}(x) = |x - \xi|^\alpha$, $0 < \xi < 1$, $\alpha > 0$ and $C_{\bar{w}} := \{f \in C([0, 1] \setminus \{\xi\}) : \lim_{x \rightarrow \xi} (\bar{w}f)(x) = 0\}$.

The norm in $C_{\bar{w}}$ is defined by $\|f\|_{C_{\bar{w}}} := \|\bar{w}f\| = \sup_{0 \leq x \leq 1} |(\bar{w}f)(x)|$. Define

$$W_{\bar{w}, \lambda}^2 := \{f \in C_{\bar{w}} : f' \in A.C.((0, 1)), \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda} f''\| < \infty\}.$$

For $f \in C_{\bar{w}}$, the weighted modulus of smoothness is defined by

$$\omega_{\varphi}^2(f, t)_{\bar{w}} := \sup_{0 < h \leq t} \{\|\bar{w}\Delta_{h\varphi}^2 f\|_{[16h^2, 1-16h^2]} + \|\bar{w}\overrightarrow{\Delta}_h^2 f\|_{[0, 16h^2]} + \|\bar{w}\overleftarrow{\Delta}_h^2 f\|_{[1-16h^2, 1]}\},$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{h\varphi}^2 f(x) &= f(x + h\varphi(x)) - 2f(x) + f(x - h\varphi(x)), \\ \overrightarrow{\Delta}_h^2 f(x) &= f(x + 2h) - 2f(x + h) + f(x), \\ \overleftarrow{\Delta}_h^2 f(x) &= f(x - 2h) - 2f(x - h) + f(x), \end{aligned}$$

and $\varphi(x) = \sqrt{x(1-x)}$, $\delta_n(x) = \varphi(x) + \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$.

Let

$$\psi(x) = \begin{cases} 10x^3 - 15x^4 + 6x^5, & 0 < x < 1, \\ 0, & x \leq 0, \\ 1, & x \geq 1. \end{cases}$$

Obviously, ψ is non-decreasing on the real axis, $\psi \in C^2((-\infty, +\infty))$, $\psi^{(i)}(0) = 0$, $i = 0, 1, 2$. $\psi^{(i)}(1) = 0$, $i = 1, 2$ and $\psi(1) = 1$. Further, let

$$x_1 = \frac{[n\xi - 2\sqrt{n}]}{n}, \quad x_2 = \frac{[n\xi - \sqrt{n}]}{n}, \quad x_3 = \frac{[n\xi + \sqrt{n}]}{n}, \quad x_4 = \frac{[n\xi + 2\sqrt{n}]}{n},$$

and

$$\bar{\psi}_1(x) = \psi\left(\frac{x - x_1}{x_2 - x_1}\right), \quad \bar{\psi}_2(x) = \psi\left(\frac{x - x_3}{x_4 - x_3}\right).$$

Consider

$$P(x) := \frac{x - x_4}{x_1 - x_4} f(x_1) + \frac{x_1 - x}{x_1 - x_4} f(x_4),$$

the linear function joining the points $(x_1, f(x_1))$ and $(x_4, f(x_4))$. And let

$$\bar{F}_n(f, x) := \bar{F}_n(x) = f(x)(1 - \bar{\psi}_1(x) + \bar{\psi}_2(x)) + \bar{\psi}_1(x)(1 - \bar{\psi}_2(x))P(x).$$

From the above definitions it follows that

$$\bar{F}_n(f, x) = \begin{cases} f(x), & x \in [0, x_1] \cup [x_4, 1], \\ f(x)(1 - \bar{\psi}_1(x)) + \bar{\psi}_1(x)P(x), & x \in [x_1, x_2], \\ P(x), & x \in [x_2, x_3], \\ P(x)(1 - \bar{\psi}_2(x)) + \bar{\psi}_2(x)f(x), & x \in [x_3, x_4]. \end{cases}$$

Evidently, $\bar{F}_n$ is a positive linear operator which depends on the functions values $f(k/n)$, $0 \leq k/n \leq x_2$ or $x_3 \leq k/n \leq 1$, it reproduces linear functions, and $\bar{F}_n \in C^2([0, 1])$ provided

$f \in W_{\bar{w}, \lambda}^2$. Now for every $f \in C_{\bar{w}}$ define the Bernstein type operator

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{B}_n(f, x) &:= B_n(\bar{F}_n(f), x) \\ &= \sum_{k/n \in [0, x_1] \cup [x_4, 1]} p_{n,k}(x) f\left(\frac{k}{n}\right) + \sum_{x_2 < k/n < x_3} p_{n,k}(x) P\left(\frac{k}{n}\right) \\ &\quad + \sum_{x_1 < k/n < x_2} p_{n,k}(x) \left\{ f\left(\frac{k}{n}\right) \left(1 - \bar{\psi}_1\left(\frac{k}{n}\right)\right) + \bar{\psi}_1\left(\frac{k}{n}\right) P\left(\frac{k}{n}\right) \right\} \\ &\quad + \sum_{x_3 < k/n < x_4} p_{n,k}(x) \left\{ P\left(\frac{k}{n}\right) \left(1 - \bar{\psi}_2\left(\frac{k}{n}\right)\right) + \bar{\psi}_2\left(\frac{k}{n}\right) f\left(\frac{k}{n}\right) \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (1.1)$$

Obviously, $\bar{B}_n$ is a positive linear operator, $\bar{B}_n(f)$ is a polynomial of degree at most n , it preserves linear functions, and depends only on the function values $f(k/n)$, $k/n \in [0, x_2] \cup [x_3, 1]$. Now we state our main results as follows:

Theorem 1. If $\alpha > 0$, for any $f \in C_{\bar{w}}$, we have $\|\bar{w} \bar{B}_n''(f)\| \leq C n^2 \|\bar{w} f\|$.

Theorem 2. For any $\alpha > 0$, $0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$, we have

$$|\bar{w}(x) \varphi^{2\lambda}(x) \bar{B}_n''(f, x)| \leq \begin{cases} C n \{ \max\{n^{1-\lambda}, \varphi^{2(\lambda-1)}\} \} \|\bar{w} f\|, & f \in C_{\bar{w}}, \\ C \|\bar{w} \varphi^{2\lambda} f''\|, & f \in W_{\bar{w}, \lambda}^2. \end{cases}$$

Theorem 3. For $f \in C_{\bar{w}}$, $0 < \xi < 1$, $\alpha > 0$, $\alpha_0 \in (0, 2)$, we have

$$\bar{w}(x) |f(x) - \bar{B}_n(f, x)| = O\left((n^{-\frac{1}{2}} \varphi^{-\lambda}(x) \delta_n(x))^{\alpha_0}\right) \iff \omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^2(f, t)_{\bar{w}} = O(t^{\alpha_0}).$$

2 Lemmas

Lemma 1. ([9]) For any non-negative real u and v , we have

$$\sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \left(\frac{k}{n}\right)^{-u} \left(1 - \frac{k}{n}\right)^{-v} p_{n,k}(x) \leq C x^{-u} (1-x)^{-v}. \quad (2.1)$$

Lemma 2. ([2]) For any $\alpha > 0$, $f \in C_{\bar{w}}$, we have

$$\|\bar{w} \bar{B}_n(f)\| \leq C \|\bar{w} f\|. \quad (2.2)$$

Lemma 3. ([8]) If $\varphi(x) = \sqrt{x(1-x)}$, $0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$, $0 \leq \beta \leq 1$, then

$$\int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \cdots \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \varphi^{-r\beta} \left(x + \sum_{k=1}^r u_k\right) du_1 \cdots du_r \leq C h^r \varphi^{r(\lambda-\beta)}(x). \quad (2.3)$$

Lemma 4. ([2]) If $\gamma \in R$, then

$$\sum_{k=0}^n p_{n,k}(x) |k - nx|^\gamma \leq C n^{\frac{\gamma}{2}} \varphi^\gamma(x). \quad (2.4)$$

Lemma 5. Let $A_n(x) := \bar{w}(x) \sum_{|k-n\xi| \leq \sqrt{n}} p_{n,k}(x)$. Then $A_n(x) \leq C n^{-\alpha/2}$ for $0 < \xi < 1$ and $\alpha > 0$.

Proof. If $|x - \xi| \leq \frac{3}{\sqrt{n}}$, then the statement is trivial. Hence assume $0 \leq x \leq \xi - \frac{3}{\sqrt{n}}$ (the case $\xi + \frac{3}{\sqrt{n}} \leq x \leq 1$ can be treated similarly). Then for a fixed x the maximum of $p_{n,k}(x)$ is attained for $k = k_n := [n\xi - \sqrt{n}]$. By using Stirling's formula, we get

$$\begin{aligned} p_{n,k_n}(x) &\leq C \frac{\left(\frac{n}{e}\right)^n \sqrt{nx}^{k_n} (1-x)^{n-k_n}}{\left(\frac{k_n}{e}\right)^{k_n} \sqrt{k_n} \left(\frac{n-k_n}{e}\right)^{n-k_n} \sqrt{n-k_n}} \\ &\leq \frac{C}{\sqrt{n}} \left(\frac{nx}{k_n}\right)^{k_n} \left(\frac{n(1-x)}{n-k_n}\right)^{n-k_n} \\ &= \frac{C}{\sqrt{n}} \left(1 - \frac{k_n - nx}{k_n}\right)^{k_n} \left(1 + \frac{k_n - nx}{n - k_n}\right)^{n-k_n}. \end{aligned}$$

Now from the inequalities

$$k_n - nx = [n\xi - \sqrt{n}] - nx > n(\xi - x) - \sqrt{n} - 1 \geq \frac{1}{2}n(\xi - x),$$

and

$$1 - u \leq e^{-u - \frac{1}{2}u^2}, \quad 1 + u \leq e^u, \quad u \geq 0,$$

it follows that the second inequality is valid. To prove the first one we consider the function $\lambda(u) = e^{-u - \frac{1}{2}u^2} + u - 1$. Here $\lambda(0) = 0$, $\lambda'(u) = -(1+u)e^{-u - \frac{1}{2}u^2} + 1$, $\lambda'(0) = 0$, $\lambda''(u) = u(u+2)e^{-u - \frac{1}{2}u^2} \geq 0$, whence $\lambda(u) \geq 0$ for $u \geq 0$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} p_{n,k_n}(x) &\leq \frac{C}{\sqrt{n}} \exp\left\{k_n \left[-\frac{k_n - nx}{k_n} - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{k_n - nx}{k_n}\right)^2\right] + k_n - nx\right\} \\ &= \frac{C}{\sqrt{n}} \exp\left\{-\frac{(k_n - nx)^2}{2k_n}\right\} \leq e^{-Cn(\xi-x)^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus $A_n(x) \leq C(\xi - x)^\alpha e^{-Cn(\xi-x)^2}$. An easy calculation shows that here the maximum is attained when $\xi - x = \frac{C}{\sqrt{n}}$ and the lemma follows. $\square$

Lemma 6. For $0 < \xi < 1$, $\alpha, \beta > 0$, we have

$$\bar{w}(x) \sum_{|k-n\xi| \leq \sqrt{n}} |k - nx|^\beta p_{n,k}(x) \leq Cn^{(\beta-\alpha)/2} \varphi^\beta(x). \quad (2.5)$$

Proof. By (2.4) and the lemma 5, we have

$$\bar{w}(x)^{\frac{1}{2n}} (\bar{w}(x) \sum_{|k-n\xi| \leq \sqrt{n}} p_{n,k}(x))^{\frac{2n-1}{2n}} \left(\sum_{|k-n\xi| \leq \sqrt{n}} |k - nx|^{2n\beta} p_{n,k}(x) \right)^{\frac{1}{2n}} \leq Cn^{(\beta-\alpha)/2} \varphi^\beta(x). \square$$

Lemma 7. For any $\alpha > 0$, $f \in W_{\bar{w},\lambda}^2$, we have

$$\bar{w}(x) |f(x) - P(f, x)|_{[x_1, x_4]} \leq C \left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n} \varphi^\lambda(x)} \right)^2 \|\bar{w} \varphi^{2\lambda} f''\|. \quad (2.6)$$

Proof. If $x \in [x_1, x_4]$, for any $f \in W_{\bar{w},\lambda}^2$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} f(x_1) &= f(x) + f'(x)(x_1 - x) + \int_{x_1}^x (t - x_1) f''(t) dt, \\ f(x_4) &= f(x) + f'(x)(x_4 - x) + \int_{x_4}^x (t - x_4) f''(t) dt, \\ \delta_n(x) &\sim \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}, \quad n = 1, 2, \dots \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{w}(x)|f(x) - P(f, x)| &\leq \bar{w}(x)\left|\frac{x - x_4}{x_1 - x_4}\right| \int_{x_1}^x |(t - x_1)f''(t)|dt \\ &\quad + \bar{w}(x)\left|\frac{x_1 - x}{x_1 - x_4}\right| \int_{x_4}^x |(t - x_4)f''(t)|dt \\ &:= I_1 + I_2. \end{aligned}$$

Whence t is between x_1 and x . We have $\frac{|t-x_1|}{\bar{w}(t)} \leq \frac{|x-x_1|}{\bar{w}(x)}$, then

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &\leq C\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}f''\| |(x - x_1)(x - x_4)| \int_{x_1}^x \varphi^{-2\lambda}(t)dt \\ &\leq C\left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\varphi^\lambda(x)}\right)^2 \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}f''\|. \end{aligned}$$

Analogously, we have

$$I_2 \leq C\left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\varphi^\lambda(x)}\right)^2 \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}f''\|.$$

Now the lemma follows from combining these results together. $\square$

3 Proof of Theorem

3.1 Proof of Theorem 1

If $f \in C_{\bar{w}}$, when $x \in [\frac{1}{n}, 1 - \frac{1}{n}]$, by [2], we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\bar{w}(x)\bar{B}_n''(f, x)| &\leq n\varphi^{-2}(x)\bar{w}(x)|\bar{B}_n(f, x)| \\ &\quad + \bar{w}(x)\varphi^{-4}(x) \sum_{k=0}^n p_{n,k}(x)|k - nx|\left|\bar{F}_n\left(\frac{k}{n}\right)\right| \\ &\quad + \bar{w}(x)\varphi^{-4}(x) \sum_{k=0}^n (k - nx)^2 \left|\bar{F}_n\left(\frac{k}{n}\right)\right| p_{n,k}(x) \\ &:= A_1 + A_2 + A_3. \end{aligned}$$

By (2.2), we have

$$A_1(x) = n\varphi^{-2}(x)\bar{w}(x)|\bar{B}_n(f, x)| \leq Cn^2\|\bar{w}f\|.$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} A_2 &= \bar{w}(x)\varphi^{-4}(x) \left[\sum_{k/n \in A} |k - nx|\left|\bar{F}_n\left(\frac{k}{n}\right)\right| p_{n,k}(x) + \sum_{x_2 \leq k/n \leq x_3} |k - nx|\left|P\left(\frac{k}{n}\right)\right| p_{n,k}(x) \right] \\ &:= \sigma_1 + \sigma_2. \end{aligned}$$

thereof $A := [0, x_2] \cup [x_3, 1]$. If $\frac{k}{n} \in A$, when $\frac{\bar{w}(x)}{\bar{w}(\frac{k}{n})} \leq C(1+n^{-\frac{\alpha}{2}}|k-nx|^\alpha)$, we have $|k-n\xi| \geq \frac{\sqrt{n}}{2}$, by (2.4), then

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1 &\leq C\|\bar{w}f\|\varphi^{-4}(x) \sum_{k=0}^n p_{n,k}(x)|k - nx|[1 + n^{-\frac{\alpha}{2}}|k - nx|^\alpha] \\ &= C\|\bar{w}f\|\varphi^{-4}(x) \sum_{k=0}^n p_{n,k}(x)|k - nx| + Cn^{-\frac{\alpha}{2}}\|\bar{w}f\|\varphi^{-4}(x) \sum_{k=0}^n p_{n,k}(x)|k - nx|^{1+\alpha} \\ &\leq Cn^{\frac{1}{2}}\varphi^{-3}(x)\|\bar{w}f\| + Cn^{\frac{1}{2}}\varphi^{-3+\alpha}(x)\|\bar{w}f\| \\ &\leq Cn^2\|\bar{w}f\|. \end{aligned}$$

For σ_2 , P is a linear function. We note $|P(\frac{k}{n})| \leq \max(|P(x_1)|, |P(x_4)|) := P(a)$. If $x \in [x_1, x_4]$, we have $\bar{w}(x) \leq \bar{w}(a)$. So, if $x \in [x_1, x_4]$, by (2.4), then

$$\sigma_2 \leq C\bar{w}(a)P(a)\varphi^{-4}(x) \sum_{k=0}^n p_{n,k}(x)|k - nx| \leq Cn^2\|\bar{w}f\|.$$

If $x \notin [x_1, x_4]$, then $\bar{w}(a) > n^{-\frac{\alpha}{2}}$, by (2.5), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_2 &\leq C\varphi^{-4}(x)\bar{w}(x) \sum_{x_2 \leq k/n \leq x_3} |P(a)(k - nx)|p_{n,k}(x) \\ &\leq Cn^{\frac{\alpha}{2}}\|\bar{w}f\|\varphi^{-4}(x)\bar{w}(x) \sum_{x_2 \leq k/n \leq x_3} |k - nx|p_{n,k}(x) \\ &\leq Cn^2\|\bar{w}f\|. \end{aligned}$$

So, $A_2 \leq Cn^2\|\bar{w}f\|$. Similarly, $A_3 \leq Cn^2\|\bar{w}f\|$. It follows from combining the above inequalities that the inequality is proved.

When $x \in [0, \frac{1}{n}]$ (The same as $x \in [1 - \frac{1}{n}, 1]$), by [6], then

$$\bar{B}_n''(f, x) = n(n-1) \sum_{k=0}^{n-2} \bar{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n}}^2 \bar{F}_n(\frac{k}{n}) p_{n-2,k}(x).$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned} |\bar{w}(x)\bar{B}_n''(f, x)| &\leq Cn^2\bar{w}(x) \sum_{k=0}^{n-2} |\bar{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n}}^2 \bar{F}_n(\frac{k}{n})| p_{n-2,k}(x) \\ &= Cn^2\bar{w}(x) [\sum_{k/n \in A} p_{n-2,k}(x) |\bar{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n}}^2 \bar{F}_n(\frac{k}{n})| + \sum_{x_2 \leq k/n \leq x_3} p_{n-2,k}(x) |\bar{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n}}^2 P(\frac{k}{n})|]. \end{aligned}$$

We can deal with it in accordance with the former proofs, and prove it immediately, then the theorem is done. $\square$

3.2 Proof of Theorem 2

(1) We prove the first inequality of Theorem 2.

Case 1. If $0 \leq \varphi(x) \leq \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$, by Theorem 1, we have

$$|\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2\lambda}(x)\bar{B}_n''(f, x)| \leq Cn^{-\lambda}|\bar{w}(x)\bar{B}_n''(f, x)| \leq Cn^{2-\lambda}\|\bar{w}f\|.$$

Case 2. If $\varphi(x) > \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$, by [3], we have

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{B}_n''(f, x) = B_n''(\bar{F}_n, x) &= (\varphi^2(x))^{-2} \sum_{i=0}^2 Q_i(x, n) n^i \sum_{k=0}^n (x - \frac{k}{n})^i \bar{F}_n(\frac{k}{n}) p_{n,k}(x), \\ Q_i(x, n) &= (nx(1-x))^{[(2r-i)/2]}, \\ (\varphi^2(x))^{-2} Q_i(x, n) n^i &\leq C(n/\varphi^2(x))^{1+i/2}. \end{aligned}$$

So

$$\begin{aligned}
& |\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2\lambda}(x)\bar{B}_n''(f, x)| \\
\leq & C\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2\lambda}(x)\sum_{i=0}^2\left(\frac{n}{\varphi^2(x)}\right)^{1+i/2}\sum_{k=0}^n\left|(x-\frac{k}{n})^i\bar{F}_n\left(\frac{k}{n}\right)\right|p_{n,k}(x) \\
= & C\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2\lambda}(x)\sum_{i=0}^2\left(\frac{n}{\varphi^2(x)}\right)^{1+i/2}\sum_{k/n\in A}\left|(x-\frac{k}{n})^i\bar{F}_n\left(\frac{k}{n}\right)\right|p_{n,k}(x) \\
& + C\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2\lambda}(x)\sum_{i=0}^2\left(\frac{n}{\varphi^2(x)}\right)^{1+i/2}\sum_{x_2\leq k/n\leq x_3}\left|(x-\frac{k}{n})^iP\left(\frac{k}{n}\right)\right|p_{n,k}(x) \\
:= & \sigma_1 + \sigma_2,
\end{aligned}$$

where $A := [0, x_2] \cup [x_3, 1]$. Working as in the proof of Theorem 1, we can get $\sigma_1 \leq Cn^{2-\lambda}\|\bar{w}f\|$, $\sigma_2 \leq Cn^{2-\lambda}\|\bar{w}f\|$. By bringing these facts together, we can immediately get the first inequality of Theorem 2.

(2) If $f \in W_{\bar{w}, \lambda}^2$, by $\bar{B}_n(f, x) = B_n(\bar{F}_n(f), x)$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
|\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2\lambda}(x)\bar{B}_n''(f, x)| & \leq n^2\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2\lambda}(x)\sum_{k=0}^{n-2}\left|\bar{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n}}^2\bar{F}_n\left(\frac{k}{n}\right)\right|p_{n-2,k}(x) \\
& = n^2\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2\lambda}(x)\sum_{k=1}^{n-3}\left|\bar{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n}}^2\bar{F}_n\left(\frac{k}{n}\right)\right|p_{n-2,k}(x) \\
& + n^2\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2\lambda}(x)\left|\bar{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n}}^2\bar{F}_n(0)\right|p_{n-2,0}(x) \\
& + n^2\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2\lambda}(x)\left|\bar{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n}}^2\bar{F}_n\left(\frac{n-2}{n}\right)\right|p_{n-2,n-2}(x) \\
& := I_1 + I_2 + I_3.
\end{aligned}$$

By [3], if $0 < k < n - 2$, we have

$$\left|\bar{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n}}^2\bar{F}_n\left(\frac{k}{n}\right)\right| \leq Cn^{-1}\int_0^{\frac{2}{n}}|\bar{F}_n''\left(\frac{k}{n}+u\right)|du, \quad (3.1)$$

If $k = 0$, we have

$$\left|\bar{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n}}^2\bar{F}_n(0)\right| \leq C\int_0^{\frac{2}{n}}u|\bar{F}_n''(u)|du, \quad (3.2)$$

Similarly

$$\left|\bar{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n}}^2\bar{F}_n\left(\frac{n-2}{n}\right)\right| \leq Cn^{-1}\int_{1-\frac{2}{n}}^1(1-u)|\bar{F}_n''(u)|du. \quad (3.3)$$

By (3.1), then

$$\begin{aligned}
I_1 & \leq Cn\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2\lambda}(x)\sum_{k=1}^{n-3}\int_0^{\frac{2}{n}}|\bar{F}_n''\left(\frac{k}{n}+u\right)|dup_{n-2,k}(x) \\
& = Cn\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2\lambda}(x)\sum_{k/n\in A}\int_0^{\frac{2}{n}}|\bar{F}_n''\left(\frac{k}{n}+u\right)|dup_{n-2,k}(x) \\
& + Cn\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2\lambda}(x)\sum_{x_2\leq k/n\leq x_3}\int_0^{\frac{2}{n}}|P''\left(\frac{k}{n}+u\right)|dup_{n-2,k}(x) \\
& := T_1 + T_2, \quad (3.4)
\end{aligned}$$

where $A := [0, x_2] \cup [x_3, 1]$, P is a linear function. If $\frac{k}{n} \in A$, when $\frac{\bar{w}(x)}{\bar{w}(\frac{k}{n})} \leq C(1+n^{-\frac{\alpha}{2}}|k-nx|^\alpha)$, we have $|k-n\xi| \geq \frac{\sqrt{n}}{2}$, by (2.1), (2.4) and the Theorem 2, then

$$\begin{aligned} T_1 &\leq C\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2\lambda}(x)\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}\bar{F}_n''\| \sum_{k/n \in A} p_{n-2,k}(x)\bar{w}^{-1}\left(\frac{k}{n}\right)\varphi^{-2\lambda}\left(\frac{k}{n}\right) \\ &\leq C\varphi^{2\lambda}(x)\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}\bar{F}_n''\| \sum_{k=0}^{n-2} p_{n-2,k}(x)[1+n^{-\frac{\alpha}{2}}|k-nx|^\alpha]\varphi^{-2\lambda}\left(\frac{k}{n}\right) \\ &\leq C\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}\bar{F}_n''\| \\ &\leq C\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}f''\|. \end{aligned}$$

Working as the Theorem 1, we can get

$$T_2 \leq C\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}f''\|.$$

So, we can get

$$I_1 \leq C\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}f''\|.$$

By (3.2) and the Theorem 2, we have

$$\begin{aligned} I_2 &\leq Cn^2\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2\lambda}(x)(1-x)^{n-2} \int_0^{\frac{2}{n}} u|\bar{F}_n''(u)|du \\ &\leq Cn^2\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2\lambda}(x)(1-x)^{n-2}\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}\bar{F}_n''\| \int_0^{\frac{2}{n}} u\bar{w}^{-1}(u)\varphi^{-2\lambda}(u)du \\ &\leq C\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}\bar{F}_n''\| \\ &\leq C\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}f''\|. \end{aligned} \tag{3.5}$$

Similarly,

$$I_3 \leq C\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}f''\|. \tag{3.6}$$

By bringing (3.4), (3.5) and (3.6) together, we can get the second inequality of Theorem 2. $\square$

Corollary 1. *If $\alpha > 0$ and $\lambda = 0$, we have*

$$|\bar{w}(x)\bar{B}_n''(f, x)| \leq \begin{cases} Cn^2\|\bar{w}f\|, & f \in C_{\bar{w}}, \\ C\|\bar{w}f''\|, & f \in W_{\bar{w}}^2. \end{cases}$$

Corollary 2. *If $\alpha > 0$ and $\lambda = 1$, we have*

$$|\bar{w}(x)\varphi^2(x)\bar{B}_n''(f, x)| \leq \begin{cases} Cn\|\bar{w}f\|, & f \in C_{\bar{w}}, \\ C\|\bar{w}\varphi^2f''\|, & f \in W_{\bar{w}}^2. \end{cases}$$

3.3 Proof of Theorem 3

3.3.1 The direct theorem

We know

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{F}_n(t) &= \bar{F}_n(x) + \bar{F}_n'(t)(t-x) + \int_x^t (t-u)\bar{F}_n''(u)du, \\ B_n(t-x, x) &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

According to the definition of $W_{\bar{w},\lambda}^2$, for any $g \in W_{\bar{w},\lambda}^2$, we have $\bar{B}_n(g, x) = B_n(\bar{G}_n(g), x)$.

(1) We first estimate $\bar{w}(x)|\bar{G}_n(x) - B_n(\bar{G}_n, x)|$ under the condition of $x \in [\frac{1}{n}, 1 - \frac{1}{n}]$, then $\varphi^2(x) < \frac{1}{n}$, $\delta_n(x) \sim \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$, and

$$\bar{w}(x)|\bar{G}_n(x) - B_n(\bar{G}_n, x)| = \bar{w}(x)|B_n(R_2(\bar{G}_n, t, x), x)|,$$

thereof $R_2(\bar{G}_n, t, x) = \int_x^t (t-u)\bar{G}_n''(u)du$.

It follows from $\frac{|t-u|}{\bar{w}(u)} \leq \frac{|t-x|}{\bar{w}(x)}$, u between t and x , we have

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{w}(x)|\bar{G}_n(x) - B_n(\bar{G}_n, x)| &\leq C\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}\bar{G}_n''\|\bar{w}(x)B_n\left(\int_x^t \frac{|t-u|}{\bar{w}(u)\varphi^{2\lambda}(u)}du, x\right) \\ &\leq C\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}\bar{G}_n''\|\bar{w}(x)\left(B_n\left(\int_x^t \frac{|t-u|}{\varphi^{4\lambda}(u)}|du, x\right)\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}\left(B_n\left(\int_x^t \frac{|t-u|}{\bar{w}^2(u)}du, x\right)\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \end{aligned}$$

also

$$\int_x^t \frac{|t-u|}{\varphi^{4\lambda}(u)}du \leq C\frac{(t-x)^2}{\varphi^{4\lambda}(x)}, \quad \int_x^t \frac{|t-u|}{\bar{w}^2(u)}du \leq \frac{(t-x)^2}{\bar{w}^2(x)}. \quad (3.7)$$

By (2.4) and (3.7), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{w}(x)|\bar{G}_n(x) - B_n(\bar{G}_n, x)| &\leq C\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}\bar{G}_n''\|\varphi^{-2\lambda}(x)B_n((t-x)^2, x) \\ &\leq Cn^{-1}\frac{\varphi^2(x)}{\varphi^{2\lambda}(x)}\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}\bar{G}_n''\| \\ &\leq Cn^{-1}\frac{\delta_n^2(x)}{\varphi^{2\lambda}(x)}\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}\bar{G}_n''\| \\ &= C\left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\varphi^\lambda(x)}\right)^2\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}\bar{G}_n''\|. \end{aligned}$$

(2) We estimate $\bar{w}(x)|\bar{G}_n(x) - B_n(\bar{G}_n, x)|$ under the condition of $x \in [0, \frac{1}{n})$ (The same as $x \in (1 - \frac{1}{n}, 1]$), $\varphi(x) \sim \delta_n(x)$, now

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{w}(x)|\bar{G}_n(x) - B_n(\bar{G}_n, x)| &\leq C\bar{w}(x)\sum_{k=1}^{n-1}p_{n,k}(x)\int_x^{\frac{k}{n}}\left|\left(\frac{k}{n}-u\right)\bar{G}_n''(u)\right|du \\ &\quad + C\bar{w}(x)p_{n,0}(x)\int_0^x u|\bar{G}_n''(u)|du \\ &\quad + C\bar{w}(x)p_{n,n}(x)\int_x^1|(1-u)\bar{G}_n''(u)|du \\ &:= I_1 + I_2 + I_3. \end{aligned}$$

If u between $\frac{k}{n}$ and x , we have

$$\frac{\left|\frac{k}{n}-u\right|}{\bar{w}^2(u)} \leq \frac{\left|\frac{k}{n}-x\right|}{\bar{w}^2(x)}, \quad \frac{\left|\frac{k}{n}-u\right|}{\varphi^{4\lambda}(u)} \leq \frac{\left|\frac{k}{n}-x\right|}{\varphi^{4\lambda}(x)}. \quad (3.8)$$

By (2.4) and (3.8), then

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_1 &\leq C \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}\bar{G}_n''\| \bar{w}(x) \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} p_{n,k} \int_x^{\frac{k}{n}} \frac{|\frac{k}{n}-u|}{\bar{w}(u)\varphi^{2\lambda}(u)} du \\
 &\leq C \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}\bar{G}_n''\| \bar{w}(x) \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} p_{n,k} \left(\int_x^{\frac{k}{n}} \frac{|\frac{k}{n}-u|}{\bar{w}^2(u)} du\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\int_x^{\frac{k}{n}} \frac{|\frac{k}{n}-u|}{\varphi^{4\lambda}(u)} du\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \\
 &\leq C n^{-2} \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}\bar{G}_n''\| \varphi^{-2\lambda}(x) \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} p_{n,k}(x)(k-nx)^2 \\
 &\leq C n^{-1} \frac{\varphi^2(x)}{\varphi^{2\lambda}(x)} \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}\bar{G}_n''\| \\
 &\leq C n^{-1} \frac{\delta_n^2(x)}{\varphi^{2\lambda}(x)} \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}\bar{G}_n''\| \\
 &= C \left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\varphi^\lambda(x)}\right)^2 \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}\bar{G}_n''\|. \tag{3.9}
 \end{aligned}$$

For I_2 , when u between $\frac{k}{n}$ and x , we let $k=0$, then $\frac{u}{\bar{w}(u)} \leq \frac{x}{\bar{w}(x)}$, and

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_2 &\leq C \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}\bar{G}_n''\| \bar{w}(x) p_{n,0}(x) \int_0^x u \bar{w}^{-1}(u) \varphi^{-2\lambda}(u) du \\
 &\leq C(nx)(1-x)^{n-1} \cdot n^{-1} \frac{\varphi^2(x)}{\varphi^{2\lambda}(x)} \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}\bar{G}_n''\| \\
 &\leq C \left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\varphi^\lambda(x)}\right)^2 \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}\bar{G}_n''\|. \tag{3.10}
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we have

$$I_3 \leq C \left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\varphi^\lambda(x)}\right)^2 \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}\bar{G}_n''\|. \tag{3.11}$$

By bringing (3.9), (3.10) and (3.11), we get the result. Above all, we have

$$\bar{w}(x)|G_n(x) - B_n(G_n, x)| \leq C \left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\varphi^\lambda(x)}\right)^2 \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}\bar{G}_n''\|.$$

By (2.6) and the second inequality of Theorem 2, when $g \in W_{\bar{w},\lambda}^2$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{w}(x)|g(x) - \bar{B}_n(g, x)| &\leq \bar{w}(x)|g(x) - \bar{G}_n(g, x)| + \bar{w}(x)|\bar{G}_n(g, x) - \bar{B}_n(g, x)| \\
 &\leq \bar{w}(x)|g(x) - P(g, x)|_{[x_1, x_4]} + C \left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\varphi^\lambda(x)}\right)^2 \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}\bar{G}_n''\| \\
 &\leq C \left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\varphi^\lambda(x)}\right)^2 \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}g''\|. \tag{3.12}
 \end{aligned}$$

For $f \in C_{\bar{w}}$, we choose proper $g \in W_{\bar{w},\lambda}^2$, by (2.2) and (3.12), then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{w}(x)|f(x) - \bar{B}_n(f, x)| &\leq \bar{w}(x)|f(x) - g(x)| + \bar{w}(x)|\bar{B}_n(f - g, x)| + \bar{w}(x)|g(x) - \bar{B}_n(g, x)| \\
 &\leq C(\|\bar{w}(f - g)\| + \left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\varphi^\lambda(x)}\right)^2 \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}g''\|) \\
 &\leq C\omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^2(f, \frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\varphi^\lambda(x)})_{\bar{w}}. \square
 \end{aligned}$$

3.3.2 The inverse theorem

We define the weighted main-part modulus for $D = R_+$ by

$$\begin{aligned}\Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^2(C, f, t)_{\bar{w}} &= \sup_{0 < h \leq t} \|\bar{w} \Delta_{h\varphi^\lambda}^2 f\|_{[Ch^*, \infty)}, \\ \Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^2(1, f, t)_{\bar{w}} &= \Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^2(f, t)_{\bar{w}}.\end{aligned}$$

where $C > 2^{1/\beta(0)-1}$, $\beta(0) > 0$, and h^* is given by

$$h^* = \begin{cases} (Ar)^{1/1-\beta(0)} h^{1/1-\beta(0)}, & 0 \leq \beta(0) < 1, \\ 0, & \beta(0) \geq 1. \end{cases}$$

The main-part K -functional is given by

$$K_{\varphi^\lambda}^2(f, t^2)_{\bar{w}} = \sup_{0 < h \leq t} \inf_g \{ \|\bar{w}(f - g)\|_{[Ch^*, \infty)} + t^2 \|\bar{w} \varphi^{2\lambda} g''\|_{[Ch^*, \infty)}, g' \in A.C.((Ch^*, \infty)) \}.$$

By [3], we have

$$C^{-1} \Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^2(f, t)_{\bar{w}} \leq \omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^2(f, t)_{\bar{w}} \leq C \int_0^t \frac{\Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^2(f, \tau)_{\bar{w}}}{\tau} d\tau, \quad (3.13)$$

$$C^{-1} K_{\varphi^\lambda}^2(f, t^2)_{\bar{w}} \leq \Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^2(f, t)_{\bar{w}} \leq C K_{\varphi^\lambda}^2(f, t^2)_{\bar{w}}. \quad (3.14)$$

Proof. Let $\delta > 0$, by (3.14), we choose proper g so that

$$\|\bar{w}(f - g)\| \leq C \Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^2(f, \delta)_{\bar{w}}, \quad \|\bar{w} \varphi^{2\lambda} g''\| \leq C \delta^{-2} \Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^2(f, \delta)_{\bar{w}}.$$

then

$$\begin{aligned}|\bar{w}(x) \Delta_{h\varphi^\lambda}^2 f(x)| &\leq |\bar{w}(x) \Delta_{h\varphi^\lambda}^2 (f(x) - \bar{B}_n(f, x))| + |\bar{w}(x) \Delta_{h\varphi^\lambda}^2 \bar{B}_n(f - g, x)| \\ &\quad + |\bar{w}(x) \Delta_{h\varphi^\lambda}^2 \bar{B}_n(g, x)| \\ &\leq \sum_{j=0}^2 C_2^j \left(n^{-\frac{1}{2}} \frac{\delta_n(x + (1-j)h\varphi^\lambda(x))}{\varphi^\lambda(x + (1-j)h\varphi^\lambda(x))} \right)^{\alpha_0} \\ &\quad + \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \bar{w}(x) \bar{B}_n''(f - g, x + \sum_{k=1}^2 u_k) du_1 du_2 \\ &\quad + \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \bar{w}(x) \bar{B}_n''(g, x + \sum_{k=1}^2 u_k) du_1 du_2 \\ &:= J_1 + J_2 + J_3.\end{aligned} \quad (3.15)$$

Obviously

$$J_1 \leq C(n^{-\frac{1}{2}} \varphi^{-\lambda}(x) \delta_n(x))^{\alpha_0}. \quad (3.16)$$

By Theorem 1, we have

$$\begin{aligned}J_2 &\leq Cn^2 \|\bar{w}(f - g)\| \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} du_1 du_2 \\ &\leq Cn^2 h^2 \varphi^{2\lambda}(x) \|\bar{w}(f - g)\| \\ &\leq Cn^2 h^2 \varphi^{2\lambda}(x) \Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^2(f, \delta)_{\bar{w}}.\end{aligned} \quad (3.17)$$

By the second inequality of Corollary 2 and (2.3), we have

$$\begin{aligned} J_2 &\leq Cn\|\bar{w}(f-g)\| \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \varphi^{-2}(x + \sum_{k=1}^2 u_k) du_1 du_2 \\ &\leq Cnh^2\varphi^{2(\lambda-1)}(x)\|\bar{w}(f-g)\| \\ &\leq Cnh^2\varphi^{2(\lambda-1)}(x)\Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^2(f, \delta)_{\bar{w}}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.18)$$

By the second inequality of Theorem 2 and (2.3), we have

$$\begin{aligned} J_3 &\leq C\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}g''\|\bar{w}(x) \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \bar{w}^{-1}(x + \sum_{k=1}^2 u_k)\varphi^{-2\lambda}(x + \sum_{k=1}^2 u_k) du_1 du_2 \\ &\leq Ch^2\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2\lambda}g''\| \\ &\leq Ch^2\delta^{-2}\Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^2(f, \delta)_{\bar{w}}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.19)$$

Now, by (3.16), (3.17), (3.18) and (3.19), we get

$$|\bar{w}(x)\Delta_{h\varphi^\lambda}^2 f(x)| \leq C\{(n^{-\frac{1}{2}}\delta_n(x))^{\alpha_0} + h^2(n^{-\frac{1}{2}}\delta_n(x))^{-2}\Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^2(f, \delta)_{\bar{w}} + h^2\delta^{-2}\Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^2(f, \delta)_{\bar{w}}\}.$$

When $n \geq 2$, we have

$$n^{-\frac{1}{2}}\delta_n(x) < (n-1)^{-\frac{1}{2}}\delta_{n-1}(x) \leq \sqrt{2}n^{-\frac{1}{2}}\delta_n(x),$$

Choosing proper $x, n \in N$, so that

$$n^{-\frac{1}{2}}\delta_n(x) \leq \delta < (n-1)^{-\frac{1}{2}}\delta_{n-1}(x),$$

Therefore

$$|\bar{w}(x)\Delta_{h\varphi^\lambda}^2 f(x)| \leq C\{\delta^{\alpha_0} + h^2\delta^{-2}\Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^2(f, \delta)_{\bar{w}}\}.$$

By Borens-Lorentz lemma, we get

$$\Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^2(f, t)_{\bar{w}} \leq Ct^{\alpha_0}. \quad (3.20)$$

So, by (3.20), we get

$$\omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^2(f, t)_{\bar{w}} \leq C \int_0^t \frac{\Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^2(f, \tau)_{\bar{w}}}{\tau} d\tau = C \int_0^t \tau^{\alpha_0-1} d\tau = Ct^{\alpha_0}. \square$$

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